

Modelling The Transmission Dynamics Of Malaria – Dengue Co-Infection With Mis-Diagnosis Of Malaria

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ABSTRACT

This study has investigated the possibility of co-interaction between malaria and dengue, and has used a mathematical model to project the impact of prompt and accurate diagnosis as well as misdiagnosis of malaria in a human population. The model was formulated by dividing the population into twelve (12) epidemiological subgroups at time t . The sub-models, as well as the main model for coinfection, were developed and analyzed. Results showed that in the absence of malaria, the dengue-only model undergoes backward bifurcation when the reproduction number is less than unity. Similarly, in the absence of dengue, the malaria-only model undergoes a backward bifurcation, and when there is prompt and accurate diagnosis of malaria, the model exhibits the same phenomenon of backward bifurcation. The coinfection sub-models were numerically simulated to investigate the impact of prompt and accurate diagnosis, as well as misdiagnosis, of malaria for co-infected individuals. Numerical simulation of the models showed that focusing on prompt and accurate diagnosis of malaria infection could be beneficial in reducing the population of malaria – dengue co-infected individuals. It also revealed that with maximum number of misdiagnosed cases of malaria infection, the number of co-infected cases will increase.

Keywords: Bifurcation, Coinfection, Dengue, Malaria, Misdiagnosis, Model.

INTRODUCTION

Malaria and dengue are both mosquito borne diseases in tropical regions. Both are known for high morbidity and mortality, and for being a worldwide public health concern. Dengue is a viral disease transmitted by the urban mosquito *Aedes aegypti*. According to [1,2], the estimated global incidence of dengue is about 390 million a year with about 96 million clinical manifestations. Malaria is a protozoan disease transmitted by *Anopheles* mosquito. According to the [3], about 241 million malaria infections occurred worldwide in 2020 leading to about 627,000 deaths. It is important to note that dengue fever can occur simultaneously with other virus, bacteria and protozoan infections. Reports of dengue fever and its coinfection with malaria in patients, especially in northern Nigeria, has been documented in [4,5,6]. In tropical countries such as Nigeria and India, both vectors coexist, and raises the possibility of simultaneous occurrence of malaria and dengue. Due to the fact that both diseases present similar clinical presentation, the diagnosis of malaria and dengue coinfection might be tasking [7], leading to high rate of morbidity, complications and mortality [8].

Standard distributions and classical models have been adapted to analyze the outcomes of intervention programmes on the dynamics of several infectious diseases. From probability theory to applied statistics,

models have been used extensively to optimize human efforts in this regard. For instance, [9] simulated the effects of imperfect vaccines on the spread of COVID-19 in Nigeria, while a generalized generating function was developed and used to generate the moments of the attributes of a population distribution in [10]. Also [11] developed a lifetime hybrid probability distribution with established survival and hazard rate functions and applied the hybrid distribution to estimate recovery rates and mortality rates arising from the Covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria. Along the same line, a time series model was employed to analyse infant mortality rates in some regions of Nigeria [12]. The concurrent study of population growth is essential for any nation due to the effect it can have on the country's planning and budget allocation for health exigencies such as disease outbreak and control strategies. Many countries rely on periodic censuses to get this important data, but the process is oftentimes, very costly, involving a lot of people and technologies [13]. Reference [14] developed a model to study the dynamics of COVID-19 in Ghana and to consider the impact of testing and quarantining of immigrants, contact tracing and isolation as measures in the mitigation of the spread of the disease.

Mathematical models have also been developed to study the transmission dynamics of both malaria and dengue fever infections. A mathematical Model was developed by [15] for the dynamics and control of Malaria in Nigeria, while [16] developed a non-autonomous model to study the impact of protecting humans from mosquito bites and mass killing of mosquito vectors on malaria incidence in Missira, Central Guinea. Reference [17] had earlier developed and rigorously analyzed a deterministic model for the transmission dynamics of a strain of dengue disease which allows transmission by exposed humans and mosquitoes. Similarly, [18] presented and analyzed a mathematical model for the transmission dynamics of dengue disease considering the level of awareness in the host population.

On coinfection, [19] formulated a mathematical model for malaria-cholera coinfection to investigate their synergistic relationship under treatment, while [20] presented a model to describe the dynamics of malaria and typhoid fever coinfection. Other works were [21] who formulated and analyzed a mathematical model to explore the counteraction between malaria and schistosomiasis and [22] who presented a comprehensive mathematical model for coinfection between dengue and chikungunya. Also [23] developed a deterministic coinfection model to investigate the local and global stability of dengue – malaria coinfection. A recent study is [24] who used Lyapunov function to investigate the global stability of the endemic equilibrium point of triple coinfection of malaria, dengue and typhoid.

All these are laudable and credible efforts aimed at using mathematical models to explain the dynamics of infection and coinfection of infectious diseases. This paper is therefore designed to add to the rich literature on this subject, and particularly to simulate transmission dynamics of malaria-dengue coinfection with a misdiagnosis of malaria. The study has been organized into model formulation and analysis, the numerical simulations of the models and a brief discussion of main results.

2.1 Model Description

The total human population at time t , denoted by $N_h(t)$ is divided into the following sub-populations:

susceptible individuals ($S_h(t)$), individuals exposed to dengue ($E_d(t)$), individuals exposed to malaria ($E_m(t)$), individuals infected with dengue ($I_d(t)$), infected individuals diagnosed with malaria ($I_m^D(t)$), misdiagnosed malaria-infected individuals ($I_m^M(t)$), undiagnosed malaria-infected individuals ($I_m^U(t)$), individuals who recover from dengue ($R_d(t)$), individuals who recover from malaria ($R_m(t)$),

individuals infected with both malaria and dengue (I_{md}), malaria-infected, dengue-recovered ($I_{md}^m(t)$), and malaria-recovered, dengue-infected individuals ($I_{md}^d(t)$), so that

$$N_h(t) = S_h(t) + E_a(t) + E_m(t) + I_a(t) + I_m^D(t) + I_m^M(t) + I_m^U(t) + I_{md}(t) + I_{md}^m(t) + I_{md}^d(t) + R_d(t) + R_m(t)$$

The vector (anopheles mosquito) population at time t , denoted by $N_m(t)$ is divided into susceptible anopheles mosquitoes $M_s(t)$, exposed anopheles mosquitoes ($M_e(t)$) and the infectious anopheles mosquitoes ($M_i(t)$), so that $N_m(t) = M_s(t) + M_e(t) + M_i(t)$

In the same vein, the vector (aedes aegypti) population at time t , denoted by $N_D(t)$ is divided into susceptible aedes aegypti $D_s(t)$, exposed aedes aegypti $D_e(t)$ and infectious aedes aegypti $D_i(t)$, so that $N_D(t) = D_s(t) + D_e(t) + D_i(t)$

Hence, the total vector population at time t , is given by $N_V(t) = N_M(t) + N_D(t)$

It is assumed that susceptible humans are recruited into the population at a constant rate Λ_h .

Susceptible individuals acquire malaria infection following effective contact with infected anopheles mosquitoes (at a rate λ_m , and acquire dengue infection following effective contact with infected aedes aegypti (λ_d). It is also assumed that individuals with malaria (dengue) infection may recover a rate τ_m (τ_d). Furthermore, natural death occurs in all human subpopulations at a rate μ_h . Humans acquire malaria infection following effective contact with infected anopheles mosquitoes at a rate λ_m given by

$$\lambda_m = \frac{\beta_m b_m M_i}{N_h}$$

where β_m is the transmission probability per bite and b_m is the per capita biting rate of anopheles mosquitoes. The incidence function above is obtained by taking into account that the total number of bites made by mosquitoes equals the number of bites received by the human hosts [25]. Similarly, individuals acquire dengue infection following effective contact with infected aedes aegypti at a rate λ_d , given by

$$\lambda_d = \frac{\beta_d b_d D_i}{N_h},$$

where β_d is the transmission probability per bite and b_d is the per capital biting rate of aedes aegypti.

Susceptible individuals infected with malaria move to the exposed class (E_m) at the rate λ_m , and then progress to the diagnosed infections class (at a rate k), undiagnosed infectious class (at a rate $(1 - \sigma)(1 - k)$) and the misdiagnosed infectious class (at a rate $\sigma(1 - k)$). The parameter k stands for rate of diagnosis, σ accounts for the rate of misdiagnosis. Individuals in E_m , I_m^D , I_m^M and I_m^U classes can be infected with dengue at the rates $\phi_1 \lambda_d$, $\phi_3 \lambda_d$, $\phi_4 \lambda_d$ and $\phi_5 \lambda_d$ respectively, where ϕ_1, ϕ_3, ϕ_4 and ϕ_5 are modification parameters which accounts for the susceptibility to dengue infection. Individuals in the I_m^D, I_m^M and I_m^U classes recover at the rates $\tau_m, \zeta_1 \tau_m, \zeta_2 \tau_m$ respectively and suffer disease induced death at the rate $d_m, \psi_1 d_m$ and $\psi_2 d_m$ respectively. The parameters ψ_1, ψ_2 (where $\psi_1, \psi_2 \geq 1$) accounts for increased mortality of the I_m^M and I_m^D individuals in comparison to diagnosed individuals with malaria symptoms (I_m^D). The parameters ζ_1, ζ_2 (where $0 < \zeta_1 \leq 1, 0 < \zeta_2 \leq 1$) models the expected decrease in the rate of recovery of misdiagnosed (I_m^M) and undiagnosed (I_m^U) infected individuals respectively.

Susceptible individuals infected with dengue move to the exposed class (E_d) at a rate λ_d and then progress to the infectious class (I_d) upon developing clinical signs and symptoms of dengue at a rate ε . Individuals in the infectious class upon recovery progress to the recovered class at a rate τ_d and also suffer disease induced death at a rate d_1 . Individuals exposed (E_d) and infected (I_d) with dengue can acquire malaria infection at the rate $\phi_2\lambda_m$ and $\phi_6\lambda_m$ respectively where ϕ_2, ϕ_6 ($0 < \phi_2 \leq 1, 0 < \phi_6 \leq 1$) accounts for the susceptibility of individuals exposed and infected with dengue to malaria infection. Individuals who recover from dengue can also acquire malaria infection at a rate λ_m .

Dually infected individuals die due to malaria at a rate d_m and dengue at a rate d_1 . The I_{md} individuals recover from dengue at a rate θ, τ_d (where $0 < \theta \leq 1$ and accounts for slower recovery of dually infected individuals from dengue) and recover from malaria at a rate $\theta_2\tau_m$ (where $0 < \theta \leq 1$ accounts for slower recovery of dually infected individuals from malaria infection). Individuals in the I_{md}^M and I_{md}^D classes suffer disease induced mortality at the rate $\psi_3 d_m$ and d_1 respectively (both parameters ψ_3 and ε accounts for increased mortality in both classes).

Susceptible anopheles mosquitoes ($M_s(t)$) are generated at a constant λ_m , and acquire malaria infection following effective contacts with humans infected with malaria at a rate λ_{hm} , given by

$$\lambda_{hm} = \frac{\beta_{vm} b_m (\tau_m^D + \sigma_1 \tau_m^M + \sigma_2 \tau_m^U + (\alpha I_{md} + \tau_m^M) v)}{N_h}$$

where β_{vm} is the transmission probability of malaria infection, b_m is the biting rate of anopheles mosquitoes. The parameters σ_1 and σ_2 ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2 \geq 1$) are modification parameters accounting for

the increased likelihood of infection of vectors from humans who are misdiagnosed and undiagnosed in relation to diagnosed, infected individuals. Similarly, $\alpha (\alpha \geq 1)$ is a modification parameter that captures the fact that dually infected individuals are more infected than malaria-infective, dengue-recovered individuals. In the same vein, $v \geq 1$ models the fact that dually infected individuals as well as malaria-infected, dengue-recovered individuals are more infectious than diagnosed infected individuals.

The population of susceptible aedes aegypti ($D_S(t)$) acquire dengue infection following effective contacts with infectious humans at a rate

$$\lambda_{h_d} = \frac{\beta_{v_d} b_d (I_{m_d}^M + I_{m_d}^U + I_{m_d}^D)}{N_h}$$

where β_{v_d} is the transmission probability of dengue infection, b_d is the biting rate of aedes aegypti.

On the basis of the above formulation and assumptions, we have the following systems of differential equations:

System 2.1

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} = \lambda_h + \rho R_m - (\lambda_m + \lambda_d + \mu_h) S_h$$

$$\frac{dE_m}{dt} = \phi_7 \lambda_m R_d + \lambda_m S_H - (1 + \phi_1 \lambda_d + \mu_h) E_m$$

$$\frac{dE_d}{dt} = \lambda_d S_H - (\phi_2 \lambda_m + \gamma + \mu_h) E_d \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{dI_d}{dt} = \gamma E_d - (\phi_6 \lambda_m + \tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) I_d$$

$$\frac{dI_m^D}{dt} = K E_m - (\phi_3 \lambda_d + \tau_m + \mu_h + d_m) I_m^D$$

$$\frac{dI_m^M}{dt} = \varepsilon(1-k)E_m - (\phi_4\lambda_d + \zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1d_m)I_m^M$$

$$\frac{dI_m^U}{dt} = (1-\varepsilon)(1-k)E_m - (\phi_5\lambda_d + \zeta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2d_m)I_m^U$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dI_{md}}{dt} = & \phi_1\lambda_d E_m + \phi_2\lambda_m E_d + \phi_3\lambda_d I_m^D + \phi_4\lambda_d I_m^M + \phi_5\lambda_d I_m^U + \phi_6\lambda_m I_d \\ & - (\theta_1\tau_d + \theta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m + d_1)I_{md} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{dI_{md}^M}{dt} = \theta_1\tau_d I_{md} - (\theta_4\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_3d_m)I_{md}^M$$

$$\frac{dI_{md}^d}{dt} = \theta_2\tau_m I_{md} - (\theta_3\tau_d + \mu_h + \varepsilon d_1)I_{md}^d$$

$$\frac{dR_d}{dt} = \tau_m I_m^D + \zeta_1\tau_m I_m^M + \zeta_2\tau_m I_m^U + \theta_4\tau_m I_{md}^M - (\rho + \mu_h)R_m$$

$$\frac{dR_m}{dt} = \tau + d I_d + \theta_3\tau_d I_{md}^D - (\mu_h + \phi_7\lambda_m)R_d$$

$$\frac{dM_s}{dt} = \lambda_m - (\lambda_{hm} + \mu_m)M_s$$

$$\frac{dM_e}{dt} = \lambda_{hm}M_s - (\delta_2 + \mu_m)M_e$$

$$\frac{dM_i}{dt} = \delta_2M_e - \mu_m M_i$$

$$\frac{dD_s}{dt} = \lambda_d - (\lambda_{hd} + \mu_d)D_s$$

Table 1: Description of State Variables and Parameters of System 2.1

Variable	Description
$S_h(t)$	Individuals susceptible to malaria and dengue infection
$E_d(t)$	Individuals exposed to dengue infection
$E_m(t)$	Individuals exposed to malaria infection
$I_d(t)$	Individuals infected with dengue
$I_m^D(t)$	Infected individuals diagnosed of malaria
$I_m^M(t)$	Malaria infected individuals who are misdiagnosed
$I_m^U(t)$	Undiagnosed malaria infected individuals
I_{md}	Dually infected individuals with malaria and dengue
I_{md}^M	Malaria-infected, dengue-recovered individuals
I_{md}^D	Malaria-recovered, dengue-infected individuals
R_d	Individuals who recover from dengue
R_m	Individuals who recover from malaria
Λ_h	Constant human recruitment rate
Λ_m	Recruitment rate of anopheles mosquitoes
Λ_d	Recruitment rate of aedes aegypti
μ_h	Natural death rate of humans
μ_m	Death rate of anopheles mosquitoes
μ_d	Death rate of aedes aegypti
λ_m	Infectious rate of anopheles mosquitoes
λ_d	Infectious rate of aedes aegypti
β_{vm}	Transmission probability from humans to malaria vector

β_m	Transmission probability from malaria vectors to human
β_d	Transmission probability from dengue vectors to human
b_m	Biting rate of anopheles mosquitoes
b_d	Biting rate of aedes aegypti
k	Rate of malaria diagnosis
ε	Rate of malaria misdiagnosis
σ	Rate of progression of dengue infected class
τ_d	Treatment rate of dengue
τ_m	Treatment rate of malaria
d_m	Malaria induced death rate
d_1	Dengue induced death rate
$\phi_1, \phi_3, \phi_4, \phi_5$	Modification parameters that account for susceptibility to dengue infection
ϕ_2, ϕ_6, ϕ_7	Modification parameters that account for susceptibility to malaria infection
θ_2, θ_4	Modification parameters that account for slower rate of recovery in the I_{md} and I_{md}^M classes respectively.
θ_1, θ_3	Modification parameters that account for slower rate of recovery from dengue in the I_{md} and I_{md}^D classes respectively
ζ_1, ζ_2	Modification parameters for reduced rate of recovered in the misdiagnosed and undiagnosed classes
ψ_1, ψ_2, ψ_3	Modification parameters for increased disease induced death rates in the I_m^M, I_m^U and I_{md}^M classes respectively
λ_{hm}	Transmission rate from infected humans to anopheles mosquitoes
λ_{hd}	Transmission rate from infected humans to aedes aegypti
δ_1	Rate of progression from exposed aedes aegypti to infectious aedes aegypti

δ_2	Rate of progression from exposed anopheles mosquito to infected anopheles mosquito.
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2.2 Well – posedness of Model (2.1)

In this section, we show that the system (2.1) is mathematically well defined and epidemiologically meaningful by showing that all its state variables are non-negative for all time (t). Since the model (2.1) monitors the human population, then, the solutions of model (2.1) with non-negative initial data will remain positive for all time $t \geq 0$.

Lemma 2.1:

The system (2.1) preserves positivity of solutions. This implies that the solution with positive initial conditions will remain positive for all time $t > 0$.

Proof:

Suppose

$$t_1 = \sup\{t > 0: S_H(t) > 0, E_m(t) > 0, E_d(t) > 0, I_d(t) > 0, I_m^D(t) > 0, I_m^M(t) > 0, I_m^W(t) > 0, I_{md}(t) > 0, I_{md}^M > 0, I_{md}^D > 0, R_m(t) > 0, R_d(t) > 0, M_s(t) > 0, M_e(t) > 0, M_i(t) > 0, D_s(t) > 0, D_e(t) > 0, D_i(t) > 0\} > 0$$

(2.2)

From the first equation of model (2.1), it follows that

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} = \Lambda_h + \rho R_m - (\lambda_m + \lambda_d + \mu_h)S_h$$

which implies that

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} \leq \Lambda_h - (\lambda_m + \lambda_d + \mu_h)S_h \quad (2.3)$$

Solving the above gives

$$S_h(t_1) = S_h(0) \exp \left[-\mu_h t_1 - \int_0^{t_1} (\lambda_m(\tau) + \lambda_d(\tau)) d(\tau) \right] \quad (2.4)$$

$$= \left\{ \exp \left[-\mu_h t_1 - \int_0^{t_1} (\lambda_h(t) + \lambda_d(\tau)) d(\tau) \right] - \int_0^{t_1} \Lambda_h \left[\exp \left(\mu_h y + \int_0^y (\lambda_m(\tau) + \lambda_d(\tau)) dy > 0 \right) \right] \right\}$$

Similarly, using the same approach of integrating factor, we can show that all the state variables of model (2.1) will remain positive for all time $t > 0$.

Lemma 2.2:

The feasible region Ω is given by

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \{S_h, E_m, E_d, I_d, I_m^D, I_m^M, I_m^U, I_{md}, I_{md}^M, \\ I_{md}^D, R_m, R_d\} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{12} : N_h \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} \\ (M_s, M_e, M_i) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3 : N_m \leq \frac{\Lambda_m}{\mu_m}, \\ (D_s, D_e, D_i) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3 : N_d \leq \frac{\Lambda_d}{\mu_d} \end{array} \right. \quad (2.5)$$

is positively invariant and attracting for model (2.1)

Proof:

From (2.1), add the first twelve equations to get (2.6). Add the thirteenth, fourteenth and fifteenth equations to get (2.7) and add the last three equations to get (2.8)

$$\frac{dN_h}{dt} = \Lambda_h - \mu_h N_h - (d_1 I_d + d_m I_m^D + \psi_1 d_m I_m^M + \psi_2 d_m I_m^U + (d_m + d_1) I_{md} + \psi_3 d_m I_{md}^M + \epsilon d_1 I_{md}^D)$$

(2.6)

$$\frac{dN_m}{dt} = \Lambda_m - \mu_m N_m \quad (2.7)$$

$$\frac{dN_d}{dt} = \Lambda_d - \mu_d N_d \quad (2.8)$$

For (2.6), we have $\frac{dN_h}{dt} \leq \Lambda_h - \mu_h N_h$

Which implies that $\frac{dN_h}{dt} + \mu_h N_h \leq \Lambda_h$

Solving the inequality gives

$$N_h(t) \leq N_h(0)e^{-(\mu_h t)} + \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} (1 - e^{-\mu_h t}) \quad (2.9)$$

Similarly from (2.7) we have,

$$N_m(t) \leq N_m(0)e^{-\mu_h t} + \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} (1 - e^{-\mu_h t}) \quad (2.10)$$

and from (2.8) we have

$$N_d(t) \leq N_d(0)e^{-\mu_h t} + \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} (1 - e^{-\mu_h t}) \quad (2.11)$$

In particular,

$$N_h(t) \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} \text{ if } N_h(0) \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h},$$

$$N_m(t) \leq \frac{\Lambda_m}{\mu_m} \text{ if } N_m(0) \leq \frac{\Lambda_m}{\mu_m}$$

$$\text{and } N_d(t) \leq \frac{\Lambda_d}{\mu_d} \text{ if } N_d(0) \leq \frac{\Lambda_d}{\mu_d} \text{ for all } t > 0$$

Thus, Ω is positively invariant under the flow described by model (2.1). We can study system (2.1) in the feasible region Ω as it is mathematically and epidemiologically well-posed.

2.3 Analysis of Dengue-only Sub-Model

In order to analyze the dynamics of the full model (2.1), it is instructive to gain insight into the dynamics of the sub-models, i. e Dengue-only and Malaria-only models.

We begin by analyzing the dengue-only model. This is obtained by setting

$$E_m = I_m^D = I_m^M = I_m^W = I_{md} = I_{md}^M = I_{md}^D = R_m = M_s = M_e = M_i = 0 \text{ in (2.1).}$$

The system becomes

$$\frac{dS_H}{dt} = \Lambda_h - (\lambda_d + \mu_h)S_H$$

$$\frac{dE_d}{dt} = \lambda_d S_H - (\varepsilon + \mu_h)E_d$$

$$\frac{dI_d}{dt} = \varepsilon E_d - (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)I_d$$

$$\frac{dR_d}{dt} = \tau_d I_d - (\mu_h)R_d \quad (2.12)$$

$$\frac{dD_s}{dt} = \Lambda_d - (\lambda_{hd} + \mu_d)D_s$$

$$\frac{dD_\varepsilon}{dt} = \lambda_{hd} D_s - (\delta_1 + \mu_d)D_\varepsilon$$

$$\frac{dD_i}{dt} = \delta_1 D_\varepsilon - \mu_d D_i$$

Consider the region,

$$\Omega_d = \begin{cases} (S_H, E_d, I_d, R_d) \in \mathbb{R}_+^4: N_h \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} \\ (D_s, D_\varepsilon, D_i) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3: N_d \leq \frac{\Lambda_d}{\mu_d} \end{cases} \quad (2.13)$$

Following the proofs of Lemma 2.1 and Lemma 2.2, it follows that the state variables in model (2.12) are all positive for all $t > 0$ and that the set Ω_d is positively invariant and a global attractor of all positive solutions of sub-model (2.12).

Let us now consider the dynamics of model (2.12).

2.3.1 Disease-Free Equilibrium (DFE)

The dengue-only model (2.12) has a DFE, given by

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_d &= (S_h^*, E_d^*, I_d^*, R_d^*, D_S^*, D_e^*, D_i^*) \\ &= \left(\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}, 0, 0, 0, \frac{\Lambda_d}{\mu_d}, 0, 0 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

The stability of the equilibrium given by (2.14) will be investigated using the next generation operator [26,27]. Using the notation in [27] on the model (2.12), the matrices F (of new infection

terms) and V (of the transition terms) are respectively given by $F =$

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \beta_d b_d \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d v_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_d} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta_d b_d \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d v_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_d} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ V &= \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon + \mu_h & 0 & 0 \\ -\varepsilon & \tau_d + \mu_h + d_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta_1 + \mu_d \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon + \mu_h & 0 & 0 & \beta_d b_d \\ -\varepsilon & \tau_d + \mu_h + d_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta_1 + \mu_d & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta_1 & \mu_d \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

So that

$$FV^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta_d b_d}{\delta_1 + \mu_d} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d \mu_d}{\Lambda_h \mu_d (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

It follows that the associated basic reproduction number denoted by R_{Od} is given by

$$R_{Od} = (\beta_d \beta_{vd} b_d^2 \Lambda_d \mu_h \varepsilon \delta_1)^{1/2} (\Lambda_h \mu_d^2 (\varepsilon + \mu_h) (\delta_1 + \mu_d) (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1))^{-1/2} \quad (2.15)$$

Using theorem 2 established in [28], the following result is established.

Lemma 2.3:

The DFE of the dengue-only model (2.12) is locally asymptotically stable (LAS) if $R_{Od} < 1$ and unstable if $R_{Od} > 1$.

The basic reproduction number (R_{Od}) measures the average number of new infections generated by a single infected individual in a susceptible population. The implication of this is that dengue can be eliminated from the community (when $R_{Od} < 1$) if the initial sizes of the sub-populations of the model are in the basin of attraction of the DFE (ε_d). If $R_{Od} < 1$, then an average infected individual produces less than one infection over its infectious period and the infection dies out. This implies that if $R_{Od} > 1$, then an average infected individual produces more than one infection over its infectious period and this leads to an outbreak of the disease in the population.

2.3.2 Endemic Equilibrium Point (EEP) of the Dengue-Only Model

We denote the EEP of model (2.12) by

$$\varepsilon_d^* = \{S_h^{**}, E_d^{**}, I_d^{**}, R_d^{**}, D_S^{**}, D_e^{**}, D_i^{**}\} \quad (2.16)$$

Solving the dengue-only model (2.12) at steady state gives

$$S_h^{**} = \frac{\Lambda_h}{\lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h}$$

$$E_d^{**} = \frac{\Lambda_h \lambda_d^{**}}{(\varepsilon + \mu_h)(\lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h)} \quad (2.17)$$

$$I_d^{**} = \{\varepsilon \Lambda_h \lambda_d^{**}\} / \{(\varepsilon + \mu_h)(\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)(\lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h)\}$$

$$R_d^{**} = \{\tau_d \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**}\} / \{\mu_h(\varepsilon + \mu_h)(\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)(\lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h)\}$$

$$D_S^{**} = \{\Lambda_d [\Lambda_v \mu_h (\varepsilon + \mu_h)(\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) + \Lambda_h \mu_h (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) \lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h \Lambda_d \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**} + \tau_d \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**}]\} / \{\beta_{ud} b_d \varepsilon \Lambda_h \mu_h \lambda_d^{**} + \mu_d [\Lambda_h \mu_h (\varepsilon + \mu_h)(\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) + \Lambda_h \mu_h (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) \lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**} + \tau_d \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**}]\}$$

$$D_e^{**} = \{\beta_{ud} b_d \varepsilon \Lambda_h \mu_h \Lambda_d \lambda_d^{**}\} / \{(\delta_1 + \mu_d) [\beta_{ud} b_d \varepsilon \Lambda_h \mu_h \lambda_d^{**} + \mu_d [\Lambda_h \mu_h (\varepsilon + \mu_h)(\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) + \Lambda_h \mu_h (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) \lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**} + \tau_d \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**}]]\}$$

$$D_i^{**} = \{\beta_{ud} \beta_d b_d \varepsilon \delta_1 \Lambda_h \mu_h \Lambda_d \lambda_d^{**}\} / \{[\mu_d (\delta_1 + \mu_d) (\beta_{ud} b_d \varepsilon \Lambda_h \mu_h \lambda_d^{**} + \mu_d [\Lambda_h \mu_h (\varepsilon + \mu_h)(\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) + \Lambda_h \mu_h (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) \lambda_d^{**} + \mu_h \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**} + \tau_d \Lambda_h \varepsilon \lambda_d^{**}])]\}$$

where $\lambda_d^{**} = \frac{\beta_d b_d D_i^{**}}{S_h^{**} + E_d^{**} + I_d^{**} + R_d^{**}}$ (2.18)

and $\lambda_{hd}^{**} = \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d I_d^{**}}{S_h^{**} + E_d^{**} + I_d^{**} + R_d^{**}}$ (2.19)

Substituting (2.17) and (2.19) into (2.18) shows that the endemic equilibrium of the dengue-only model (2.12) satisfy the following polynomial

$$\lambda_d^{**} [c_2 (\lambda_d^{**})^2 + c_1 (\lambda_d^{**}) + c_0] = 0 \quad (2.20)$$

where

$$c_2 = \Lambda_h^2 \mu_d (\delta_1 + \mu_d) [\beta_{vd} b_d \varepsilon \mu_h (\mu_h (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) + \varepsilon (\mu_h + \tau_d)) + 2\mu_h \mu_d \varepsilon (\varepsilon \tau_d + (\mu_h + \tau_d) (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)) + \mu_d (\varepsilon^2 (\mu_h^2 + \tau_d^2) + \mu_h^2 (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)^2)]$$

$$c_1 = \Lambda_h \mu_h (\varepsilon + \mu_h) (\tau_d + d_1) [\mu_d \Lambda_h (\delta_1 + \mu_d) (\mu_h \beta_{vd} b_d \varepsilon + 2\mu_d (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) + \varepsilon (\mu_h + \tau_d)) - \beta_{vd} \beta_d b_d^2 \varepsilon \mu_h \Lambda_d \delta_1]$$

$$c_0 = \Lambda_h^2 \mu_h^2 \mu_d^2 (\delta_1 + \mu_d) (\varepsilon + \mu_h) (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1) [1 - R_{0d}^2]$$

The root $\lambda_d^{**} = 0$ of (2.20) corresponds to the DFE ε_d^* in which its stability has already been analyzed. It is pertinent to more that c_0 is always positive, while c_2 is positive (or negative) if R_{0d} is less than (or greater than) unity, hence, we establish the following result.

Lemma 2.4: The dengue only model (2.12) has

- i) a unique endemic equilibrium if $c_0 < 0$ (whenever $R_{0d} > 1$)
- ii) precisely one unique endemic equilibrium if $c_1 < 0$ and $c_0 = 0$ or $c_1^2 - 4c_0c_2 = 0$
- iii) exactly two endemic equilibrium if $c_0 > 0$ ($R_{0d} < 1$), $c_1 < 0$ and $c_1^2 - 4c_0c_2 > 0$
- iv) no endemic equilibrium otherwise.

The possible presence of two endemic equilibria as in case (iii) suggests the possibility of backward bifurcation in model (2.12). The phenomenon of backward bifurcation occurs when a stable DFE co-exists with a locally asymptotically stable endemic equilibrium.

2.3.3 Bifurcation Analysis of Model (2.12)

In order to establish the existence of backward bifurcation, we use the centre manifold theorem [27,28]. For, convenience, we make the following simplifications (change of variables).

$$\text{Let } S_h = x_1, E_d = x_2, I_d = x_3, R_d = x_4, D_s = x_5, D_e = x_6, D_i = x_7$$

So that $N_H = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4$ and $N_D = x_5 + x_6 + x_7$

Using vector notation $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7)^T$, then model (2.12) can be written as

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = F(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{with } F = (f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5, f_6, f_7)^T$$

$$\frac{dx_1}{dt} = \Lambda_h - (\lambda_d + \mu_h)x_1 = f_1$$

$$\frac{dx_2}{dt} = \lambda_d x_1 - (\varepsilon + \mu_h)x_2 = f_2$$

$$\frac{dx_3}{dt} = \varepsilon x_2 - (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_2)x_3 = f_3$$

$$\frac{dx_4}{dt} = \tau_d x_3 - \mu_h x_4 = f_4 \quad (2.21)$$

$$\frac{dx_5}{dt} = \Lambda_d - (\lambda_{hd} + \mu_d)x_5 = f_5$$

$$\frac{dx_6}{dt} = \lambda_{hd} x_5 - (\delta_1 + \mu_d)x_6 = f_6$$

$$\frac{dx_7}{dt} = \delta_1 x_6 - \mu_d x_7 = f_7$$

with

$$\lambda_d = \frac{\beta_d b_d x_7}{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4} \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_{hd} = \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d x_3}{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4}$$

We evaluate the Jacobian of the transformed system (2.21) evaluated at the DFE (ε_d) . Let

$\beta_d = \beta^*$ be the bifurcation parameter. Solving for $\beta_d = \beta^*$ from $R_d = 1$ gives

$$\beta^* = \{\Lambda_h \mu_d^2 (\varepsilon + \mu_h) (\delta_1 + \mu_d) (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)\} / \{\beta_{vd} b_d^2 \Lambda_d \mu_h \varepsilon \delta_1\}$$

Thus, the Jacobian $J(\varepsilon_d)$ with $\beta_d = \beta^*$ is given as

$$J(\varepsilon_d) = \begin{bmatrix} -\mu_h & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\beta_d b_d \\ 0 & -\rho_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta_d b_d \\ 0 & \varepsilon & -\rho_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau_d & -\mu_h & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -J_1 & 0 & -\mu_d & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & J_1 & 0 & 0 & -\rho_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \delta_1 & -\mu_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.22)$$

where

$$\rho_1 = \varepsilon + \mu_h, \rho_2 = \tau_d + \mu_h + d_1, \rho_3 = \delta_1 + \mu_d \text{ and } J_1 = \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d \mu_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_d}$$

Now, we show that (2.22) written as $J_{\beta^*}(\varepsilon_d)$ has a right eigen vector given by

$(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4, \omega_5, \omega_6, \omega_7)^T$, where

$$\omega_1 = -\frac{\beta_d b_d \omega_7}{\mu_h}, \omega_2 = \frac{\beta_d b_d \omega_7}{\varepsilon + \mu_h}, \omega_3 = \frac{\varepsilon \omega_2}{(\tau + \mu_h + d_1)}, \omega_4 = \frac{\tau_d \omega_3}{\mu_h}, \omega_5 = -\frac{\beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d \mu_h \omega_3}{\Lambda_h \mu_d^2}$$

$$\omega_6 = \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d \mu_h \omega_3}{\delta_1 + \mu_d}, \omega_7 = \frac{\delta_1 \beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d \mu_h \omega_3}{\mu_d (\delta_1 + \mu_d)}$$

Similarly, $J_{\beta^*}(\varepsilon_d)$ has a left eigen vector $v = (v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7)$, where

$$v_1 = 0, v_4 = 0, v_5 = 0. v_2 = \frac{\varepsilon v_3}{\varepsilon + \mu_h}, v_3 = \frac{\beta_{vd} b_d \Lambda_d \mu_h \delta_1 v_7}{\Lambda_h \mu_d (\delta_1 + \mu_d) (\tau_d + \mu_h + d_1)}$$

$$v_6 = \frac{\delta_1 v_7}{\delta_1 + \mu_d} \quad \text{and} \quad v_7 = \frac{\beta_d b_d \varepsilon v_3}{\mu_d (\varepsilon + \mu_h)}$$

So that the backward bifurcation parameters are given as

$$\begin{aligned} a = & 2v_2 \omega_2 \omega_7 \frac{\partial^2 f_2}{\partial x_2 \partial x_7} + 2v_2 \omega_3 \omega_7 \frac{\partial^2 f_2}{\partial x_3 \partial x_7} + 2v_2 \omega_4 \omega_7 \frac{\partial^2 f_2}{\partial x_4 \partial x_7} + 2v_0 \omega_1 \omega_3 \frac{\partial^2 f_6}{\partial x_1 \partial x_3} \\ & + 2v_6 \omega_2 \omega_3 \frac{\partial^2 f_6}{\partial x_2 \partial x_3} + 2v_6 \omega_3 \omega_4 \frac{\partial^2 f_6}{\partial x_3 \partial x_4} + 2v_6 \omega_3 \omega_5 \frac{\partial^2 f_6}{\partial x_3 \partial x_5} + 2v_6 \omega_3^2 \frac{\partial^2 f_6}{\partial x_3^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$a = \frac{-2b_d \mu_h v_6 \omega_3 \omega_7}{\Lambda_h} [Q_1 - Q_2] \quad (2.23)$$

where

$$Q_1 = \{\beta_d v_2 \Lambda_h \mu_d (\omega_2 + \omega_3 + \omega_4) + \beta_{vd} \Lambda_d \mu_h v_6 \omega_3 \omega_7 (\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 + \omega_4)\} / \{\Lambda_h \mu_d v_6 \omega_3\}$$

$$Q_2 = \frac{\beta_{vd} \Lambda_d \mu_h \omega_5 \omega_7}{\Lambda_h \mu_d} \quad \text{and} \quad b = v_2 \omega_7 b_d > 0 \quad (2.24)$$

Clearly, $b > 0$, then the direction of the bifurcation at $\beta_d = \beta^* (R_d = 1)$ depends on the sign of

a . Hence, backward bifurcation occurs for model (2.12) at $R_m = 1$ whenever

$$Q_2 > Q_1 \quad (2.25)$$

The above result is summarized below.

Theorem 2.2:

The dengue-only model (2.12) exhibits backward bifurcation at $R_d = 1$ whenever (2.25) holds (that is bifurcation coefficient a is positive)

2.4 Malaria-Only Sub-Model

We now consider the malaria-only model, obtained by setting

$$E_d = I_d = R_d = I_{md} = I_{md}^M = I_{md}^D = D_s = D_\varepsilon = D_i = 0) \text{ in 2.1)}$$

The resulting sub-model is given by

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} = \Lambda_h - (\lambda_m + \mu_h)S_h + \rho R_m$$

$$\frac{dE_m}{dt} = \lambda_m S_H - (1 + \mu_h)E_m$$

$$\frac{dI_m^D}{dt} = KE_m - (\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)I_m^D$$

$$\frac{dI_m^M}{dt} = \varepsilon(1 - k)E_m - (\phi\zeta_1 + \mu_m + \psi_1 d_m)I_m^M$$

$$\frac{dI_m^W}{dt} = (1 - \varepsilon)(1 - k)E_m - (\zeta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m)I_m^U$$

$$\frac{dR_m}{dt} = \tau_m I_m^D + \zeta_1 \tau_m I_m^M + \zeta_2 \tau_m I_m^W - (\rho + \mu_h)R_m \quad (2.26)$$

$$\frac{dM_s}{dt} = \Lambda_m - (\lambda_{hm} + \mu_m)M_s$$

$$\frac{dM_\varepsilon}{dt} = \lambda_{hm}M_s - (\delta_2 + \mu)M_\varepsilon$$

$$\frac{dM_i}{dt} = \delta_2 M_\varepsilon - \mu_m M_i$$

where $\lambda_m = \frac{\beta_m b_m M_i}{\mu_h}$, $\lambda_{hm} = \frac{\beta_m b_m (I_m^U + \sigma_1 I_m^M + \sigma_2 I_m^W)}{\mu_h}$

and $\mu_h = S_H + E_m + I_m^D + I_m^W + I_m^M + R_m$, $\mu_m = M_s + M_e + M_i$

Consider the region

$$\Omega_m = \begin{cases} (S_h, E_m, I_m^D, I_m^M, I_m^U, R_m) \in \mathbb{R}_+^6: N_h \leq \frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} \\ (M_s, M_e, M_i) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3: N_m \leq \frac{\Lambda_m}{\mu_m} \end{cases}$$

It can be easily shown that the region Ω_m is positively invariant and a global attraction of all positive solution of sub-model (2.26). Thus, it is sufficient to consider the dynamics of model (2.26) in Ω_m .

2.4.1 Stability of the Disease-Free Equilibrium (DFE)

The DFE of the malaria-only model (2.26) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_m &= (S_h^*, E_m^*, I_m^{D^*}, I_m^{M^*}, I_m^{U^*}, R_m^*, M_s^*, M_e^*, M_i^*) \\ &= \left(\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, \frac{\Lambda_m}{N_m}, 0, 0 \right) \quad (2.27) \end{aligned}$$

The associated next generation matrices are given by

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta_m b_m \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_m b_m \Lambda_m \mu_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_m} & \frac{\sigma_1 \beta_m b_m \Lambda_m \mu_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_m} & \frac{\sigma_2 \beta_m b_m \Lambda_m \mu_h}{\Lambda_h \mu_m} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

V

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \mu_h & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ k & \tau_m + \mu_h + d_m & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \varepsilon(1 - k) & 0 & \zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + d_m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ (1 - k)(1 - \varepsilon) & 0 & 0 & \zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \delta_2 + \mu_m \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \delta_2 \quad \mu_m \end{bmatrix}$$

It follows that the associated reproduction number denoted by R_{0m} is given by

$$R_{0m} = (\beta_m \beta_{vm} b_m^2 \Lambda_m \mu_h \delta_2 \Lambda_h (k(\zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) + \sigma_1(1 - k)\varepsilon(\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) + \sigma_2(1 - \varepsilon)(1 - k)))^{1/2} / (\Lambda_h \mu_m^2 (1 + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m)(\delta_2 + \mu_m))^{1/2} \quad (2.28)$$

2.4.2 Endemic Equilibrium Point (EEP) of the Malaria-Only Model

Let the EEP of model (2.26) be denoted by $\epsilon_m^* = (S_h^{**}, E_m^{**}, I_m^{D**}, I_m^{U**}, I_m^{M**}, M_s^{**}, M_e^{**}, M_i^{**})$ (2.27)

Setting the right-hand sides of model (2.26) to zero and solving for the state variables, in terms of the force of infection at steady state, yields;

$$S_h^{**} = \frac{\Lambda_h}{\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h}, \quad E_m^{**} = \frac{\lambda_m^{**} \Lambda_h}{(1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)}, \quad I_m^{D**} = \frac{k \Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}}{(1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)}$$

$$I_m^{M**} = \{\varepsilon(1 - k)\Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}\} / (1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_m^{U**} &= \{(1 - \varepsilon)(1 - k)\Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}\} \\
 &\quad / \{(1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m)\} \\
 R_m^{**} &= \{\tau_m k \Lambda_h (\zeta_1 \zeta_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) \lambda_m^{**} + \zeta_1 \tau_m \varepsilon (1 - k) \Lambda_h (\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) \lambda_m^{**} + (1 - \varepsilon)(1 - k) \Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}\} / \{(1 + \mu)(\rho + \mu)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m)\} \\
 M_s^{**} &= [(\Lambda_m \Lambda_h (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \Lambda_m \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + (\tau_m + B) k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \sigma A \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + (1 + B)(1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_h^{**}) \\
 &\quad] / [k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 \sigma A \rho_5 \beta_{vm} b_m \mu_h \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**} + \mu_m (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + k \rho_4 \rho_5 (\tau_m + B) \lambda_h^{**} + \sigma A \rho_5 (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \lambda_m^{**} + (1 + B)(1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**})] \\
 M_e^{**} &= [\Lambda_m \beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 A \varepsilon \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**}) / \\
 &\quad [(\delta_2 + \mu_m) \beta_{vm} b_m \mu_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 \sigma A \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**} + \mu_m (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + k \rho_4 \rho_5 (\tau_m + B) \lambda_h^{**} + \sigma A \rho_5 (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \lambda_m^{**} + (1 + B)(1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**}) \\
 M_i^{**} &= [\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \delta_2 \Lambda_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 A \varepsilon \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**})] / [\mu_m (\delta_2 + \mu_m) (\beta_{vm} b_m \mu_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 \varepsilon A \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**}) + \mu_m (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + k \rho_4 \rho_5 (\tau_m + B) \lambda_h^{**} + \varepsilon A \rho_5 (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \lambda_m^{**} + (1 + B)(1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**})]
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $A = (1 - k)$, $B = (\rho + \mu_h)$

$$\rho_1 = 1\mu_h, \rho_3 = \tau_m + \mu_h + d_m, \rho_4 = \zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m, \rho_5 = \zeta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m, \rho_6 = \rho + \mu_h$$

,

$$S_h^{**} = \frac{\Lambda_h}{\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h}, \quad E_m^{**} = \frac{\lambda_m^{**} \Lambda_h}{(1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)}, \quad I_m^{D^{**}} = \frac{k \Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}}{(1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)}$$

$$I_m^{M^{**}} = \{\varepsilon(1 - k)\Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}\} / \{(1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)\}$$

$$I_m^{U^{**}} = \{(1 - \varepsilon)(1 - k)\Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}\} / \{(1 + \mu_h)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m)\}$$

$$R_m^{**} = \{\tau_m k \Lambda_h (\zeta_1 \zeta_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m) (\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) \lambda_m^{**} + \zeta_1 \tau_m \varepsilon (1 - k) \Lambda_h (\zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) \lambda_m^{**} + (1 - \varepsilon) (1 - k) \Lambda_h \lambda_m^{**}\} / \{(1 + \mu)(\rho + \mu)(\lambda_m^{**} + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m)\}$$

$$M_s^{**} = [(\Lambda_m \Lambda_h (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \Lambda_m \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + (\tau_m + B) k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \sigma A \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + (1 + B)(1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_h^{**})$$

$$] / [k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 \sigma A \rho_5 \beta_{vm} b_m \mu_h \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**} +$$

$$\mu_m (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + k \rho_4 \rho_5 (\tau_m + B) \lambda_h^{**} + \sigma A \rho_5 (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \lambda_m^{**} +$$

$$(1 + B)(1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**}]$$

$$M_s^{**} = [\Lambda_m \beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 A \varepsilon \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**}) /$$

$$[(\delta_2 + \mu_m) \beta_{vm} b_m \mu_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 \sigma A \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**} + \mu_m (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + k \rho_4 \rho_5 (\tau_m + B) \lambda_h^{**} + \sigma A \rho_5 (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \lambda_m^{**} + (1 + B)(1 - \sigma) A \lambda_m^{**})$$

$$M_i^{**} = [\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \delta_2 \Lambda_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 A \varepsilon \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**})] / [$$

$$\mu_m (\delta_2 + \mu_m) (\beta_{vm} b_m \mu_h (k \rho_4 \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_1 \varepsilon A \rho_5 \lambda_m^{**} + \sigma_2 (1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**}) + \mu_m (\rho_1 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 \lambda_m^{**} + k \rho_4 \rho_5 (\tau_m + B) \lambda_h^{**} + \varepsilon A \rho_5 (\zeta_1 \tau_m + B) \lambda_m^{**} + (1 + B)(1 - \varepsilon) A \lambda_m^{**})$$

]

Where $A = (1 - k)$, $B = (\rho + \mu_h)$

$$\rho_1 = 1\mu_h, \rho_3 = \tau_m + \mu_h + d_m, \rho_4 = \zeta_1 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m, \rho_5 = \zeta_2 \tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m, \rho_6 = \rho + \mu_h$$

,

$$\lambda_m^{**} = \{\beta_m b_m M_i^{**}\} / \{S_h^{**} + E_m^{**} + I_m^{D^{**}} + I_m^{M^{**}} + I_m^{U^{**}} + R_m^{**}\} \quad (2.30)$$

and

$$\lambda_{hm}^{**} = \{\beta_{vm} b_m [I_m^{D^{**}} + \sigma_1 I_m^{M^{**}} + \sigma_2 I_m^{U^{**}}]\} / \{S_h^{**} + E_m^{**} + I_m^{D^{**}} + I_m^{M^{**}} + I_m^{U^{**}} + R_m^{**}\} \quad (2.31)$$

Substituting (2.29) and (2.31) into (2.30) shows that the endemic equilibrium of the malaria-only model (2.26) satisfy the following polynomial:

$$\lambda_m^* [A_2 (\lambda_m^{**})^2 + A_1 (\lambda_m^{**}) + A_0] = 0 \quad (2.32)$$

where $A_2 = \Lambda_h^2 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 \rho_6 [\rho_4 \rho_5 (k + \rho_3 \rho_6) + (1 - \varepsilon)(\sigma_1 (1 - k) \rho_5 + \sigma_2 k)]$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +\Lambda_h^2 \varepsilon(1-k)(1+\rho+\mu_h)(\rho_5(k\rho_4+\sigma_1(1-\varepsilon)(1-k))+\varepsilon(1-k)(\sigma_2+(1+\rho+\mu_h))) \\
 & \quad +\Lambda_h^2(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)\rho_5(\zeta_1\tau_m+\rho \\
 & \quad +\mu_n)\left[k\left(\rho_4\rho_5+\sigma_2(1-n)+(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)(\sigma_1+\rho_5(\zeta_1\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n))\right)\right] \\
 & \quad +\Lambda_h^2 k\rho_4\rho_5(\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n)\left[k\rho_4\rho_5(1+\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + (1-\varepsilon)(k+\sigma_1\rho_5(1-k))\right] \\
 & \quad +2\Lambda_h^2(1-k)(1-\varepsilon)\rho_5(\zeta_1\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n)(\rho_3\rho_4\rho_5\rho_6+\varepsilon(1-k)(1+\rho+\mu_n)) \\
 & \quad +2\Lambda_h^2(1-k)\rho_4\rho_5(1+\rho+\mu_n)[\rho_3\rho_6+kn(\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n)] \\
 & \quad +2\Lambda_h^2 k\rho_4\rho_5^2(\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n)[\rho_3\rho_4\rho_6+(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)(\zeta_1\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n)]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_1 & = \Lambda_h^2 \rho_1\rho_3\rho_4\rho_5\rho_6 [\rho_5(k\rho_4+\sigma_1(1-\varepsilon)(1-k))+\sigma_2\varepsilon(1-k)] \\
 & \quad +2\Lambda_h^2\rho_1\rho_3\rho_4\rho_5\rho_6 \left[\rho_4\rho_5(\rho_3\rho_6+k(\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n)) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + (1-\varepsilon)[\rho_5(1-k)(\zeta_1\tau_m+\rho+\mu_n)+k(1+\rho+\mu_n)]\right] \\
 & \quad -\beta_{vm}b_m\Lambda_m\Lambda_h\delta_2[k\rho_4\rho_5+\sigma_1(1-k)\rho_5+\sigma_2\varepsilon(1-k)]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$A_0 = \Lambda_n^2 \mu_m^2 \rho_1^2 \rho_3^2 \rho_4^2 \rho_5^2 \rho_6^2 (\delta_2 + \mu_m) [1 - R_{0m}^2]$$

Clearly A_2 is always positive and A_0 is positive (or negative) whenever $R_{0m}^2 < 1$ (or $R_{0m} > 1$),

hence we establish the following result.

Lemma 2.6: The malaria-only model (2.26) has

- i) a unique endemic equilibrium if $A_0 < 0$ (whenever $R_{0m} > 1$)
- ii) exactly one unique endemic equilibrium if $A_1 < 0$ and $A_0 = 0$ or $A_1^2 - 4A_0A_2 = 0$
- iii) exactly two endemic equilibria if $A_0 > 0$ ($R_{0m} < 1$), $c_1 < 0$ and $A_1^2 - 4A_0A_2 > 0$
- iv) no endemic equilibrium otherwise

item (iii) suggests the possibility of backward bifurcation in model (2.26)

2.4.3 Bifurcation Analysis

Establishing the existence of backward bifurcation requires that we use the centre manifold theorem.

$$\text{Let } S_h = x_1^*, E_m = x_2^*, I_m^D = x_3^*, I_m^M = x_4^*, I_m^U = x_5^*, R_m = x_6^*, M_5 = x_7^*, M_e = x_8^*, M_i = x_9^*$$

$$\text{So that } N_h = x_1^* + x_2^* + x_3^* + x_4^* + x_5^* + x_6^* \quad \text{and} \quad N_m = x_7^* + x_8^* + x_9^*$$

$$\text{Using vector notation } \mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7, x_8, x_9)^T,$$

$$\text{then } \frac{dx}{dt} = F(\mathbf{x}) \text{ with } F = (f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5, f_6, f_7, f_8, f_9)^T$$

$$\frac{dx_1^*}{dt} = f_1 = \Lambda_n + \rho x_6^* - (\lambda_m + \mu_n)x_1^*, \quad \frac{dx_2^*}{dt} = f_2 = \lambda_m x_1^* - (1 + \mu_n)x_2^*$$

$$\frac{dx_3^*}{dt} = f_3 = knx_2^* - (\tau_m + \mu_n + d_m)x_3^*, \quad \frac{dx_4^*}{dt} = f_4 = \varepsilon(1 - k)x_2^* - (\zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_n + \psi_1 d_m)x_4^*$$

$$\frac{dx_5^*}{dt} = f_5 = (1 - \varepsilon)(1 - k)x_2^* - (\zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_n + \psi_2 d_m)x_5^* \quad (2.33)$$

$$\frac{dx_6^*}{dt} = f_6 = \tau_m x_3^* + \zeta_1\tau_m x_4^* + \zeta_2\tau_m x_5^* - (\rho + \mu_n)x_6^*, \quad \frac{dx_7^*}{dt} = f_7 = \Lambda_m - (\lambda_{nm} + \mu_m)x_7^*$$

$$\frac{dx_8^*}{dt} = f_8 = \lambda_{hm} x_7^* - (\delta_2 + \mu_m)x_8^*, \quad \frac{dx_9^*}{dt} = f_9 = \delta_2 x_8^* - \mu_m x_9^*$$

$$\text{With } \lambda_m = \{\beta_m b_m x_9^*\} / \{x_1^* + x_2^* + x_3^* + x_4^* + x_5^* + x_6^*\} \quad (2.34)$$

$$\text{and } \lambda_{hm} = \{\beta_{vm} b_m (x_3^* + \sigma_1 x_4^* + \sigma_2 x_5^*)\} / \{x_1^* + x_2^* + x_3^* + x_4^* + x_5^* + x_6^*\} \quad (2.35)$$

Next, we evaluate the Jacobian of the transformed system (2.33) evaluated at the DFE (ε_m).

Let $\beta_m = \beta^*$ be the bifurcation parameter. Solving for $\beta_m = \beta^*$ from $R_{0m} = 1$ gives

$$\beta^* = \{\Lambda\mu_m^2(1 + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m)(\delta_2 + \mu_m)\} / \{\beta_m b_m^2 \Lambda_m \mu_h \Lambda_h \delta_2 [kn(\zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m)(\zeta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) + \sigma_1 A(\varepsilon_m)(\zeta_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m) + \sigma_2(1 - \varepsilon)A]\} \quad (2.36)$$

Thus the Jacobian $J(\varepsilon_m)$ with $\beta_m = \beta^*$ is given as

$$J_{\beta^*}(\varepsilon_m) = \begin{bmatrix} -\mu_h & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\beta_m b_m \\ 0 & -\rho_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta_m b_m \\ 0 & kn & -\rho_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon(1 - k) & 0 & -\rho_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (1 - \varepsilon)(1 - k) & 0 & 0 & -\rho_5 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \tau_m & \zeta_1\tau_m & \zeta_2\tau_m & -\rho_6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -J_2 & -\sigma_1 J_2 & -\sigma_2 J_2 & 0 & -\mu_m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & J_2 & \sigma_1 J_2 & \sigma_2 J_2 & 0 & 0 & -(\delta_2 + \mu_m) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \delta_2 & -\mu_m \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.37)$$

where

$$\rho_1 = 1\mu_h, \rho_3 = \tau_m + \mu_h + d_m, \rho_4 = \zeta_1\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_1 d_m, \rho_5 = \zeta_2\tau_m + \mu_h + \psi_2 d_m, \rho_6 = \rho + \mu_h$$

We show that (2.37) has a right eigenvector given by $(\omega_1^*, \omega_2^*, \omega_3^*, \omega_4^*, \omega_5^*, \omega_6^*, \omega_7^*, \omega_8^*, \omega_9^*)^T$,

where,

$$\omega_1^* = \{(\tau_m kn\rho_4\rho_5 + \zeta_1\tau_m\varepsilon A\rho_3\rho_5 + \zeta_2\tau_m(1-\varepsilon)A\rho_3\rho_4)\omega_2^* - \beta_m b_m \rho_3\rho_4\rho_5\rho_6\omega_9^*\} / \{\mu_n\rho_3\rho_4\rho_5\rho_6\}$$

$$\omega_2^* = \frac{\beta_m b_m \omega_9^*}{\rho_1}, \quad \omega_3^* = \frac{kn\omega_2^*}{\rho_3}, \quad \omega_4^* = \frac{\varepsilon(1-k)\omega_2^*}{\rho_4}, \quad \omega_5^* = \frac{(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)\omega_2^*}{\rho_5}$$

$$\omega_6^* = \{(\tau_m kn\rho_4\rho_5 + \zeta_1\tau_m\varepsilon(1-k)\rho_3\rho_5 + \zeta_2\tau_m(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)\rho_3\rho_4)\omega_2^*\} / \{\rho_3\rho_4\rho_5\rho_6\}$$

$$\omega_7^* = \{$$

$$(-\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n \omega_2^*)(kn\rho_4\rho_5 + \sigma_1\varepsilon(1-k)\rho_3\rho_5 + \sigma_2(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)\rho_3\rho_4)\} / \{\Lambda_n \mu_m^2 \rho_3\rho_4\rho_5\}$$

$$\omega_8^* = \{(\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n \omega_2^*)(kn\rho_4\rho_5 + \sigma_1\varepsilon(1-k)\rho_3\rho_5 + \sigma_2(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)\rho_3\rho_4)\} / \{\Lambda_n \mu_m^2 \rho_3\rho_4\rho_5(\delta_2 + \mu_m)\}$$

$$\omega_9^* = \{\delta_2\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n \omega_2^*(kn\rho_4\rho_5 + \sigma_1\varepsilon(1-k)\rho_3\rho_5 + \sigma_2(1-\varepsilon)(1-k)\rho_3\rho_4)\} / \{\Lambda_n \mu_m^* \rho_3\rho_4\rho_5(\delta_2 + \mu_m)\}$$

Similarly, $J_{\beta^*}(\varepsilon_m)$ has a left eigenvector $v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_7, v_8, v_9$, where,

$$v_1^* = 0, \quad v_7^* = 0, \quad v_6^* = 0$$

$$v_2^* = \{\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n v_9^*(kn\delta_2\rho_4\rho_5 + \varepsilon(1-k)\sigma_2\delta_2\rho_3\rho_5 + (1-\varepsilon)(1-k)\sigma_2\delta_2\rho_3\rho_4)\} / \{\Lambda_n \mu_m^2 \rho_1\rho_3\rho_4\rho_5(\delta_2 + \mu_m)\}$$

$$v_3^* = \frac{\delta_2\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n v_9^*}{\Lambda_n \mu_m \rho_3(\delta_2 + \mu_m)}, \quad v_4^* = \frac{\sigma_1\delta_2\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n v_9^*}{\Lambda_n \mu_m \rho_4(\delta_2 + \mu_m)}, \quad v_5^* = \frac{\sigma_2\delta_2\beta_{vm} b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n v_9^*}{\Lambda_n \mu_m \rho_5(\delta_2 + \mu_m)}$$

$$v_8^* = \frac{\delta_2 v_9^*}{\delta_2 + \mu_m}, \quad v_9^* = \frac{\beta_m b_m v_9^*}{\mu_m}.$$

It can be shown, after some algebraic manipulations (involving the computed associated non-zero partial derivatives of F (at DFE), that

$$a = -\frac{b_m \mu_h}{\Lambda_h} [Q_3 - Q_4] \quad (2.38)$$

where

$$Q_3 = \frac{\beta_{vm} \Lambda_m \mu_h v_8}{\Lambda_h \mu_m} [2(\omega_3(\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3) + \omega_4 \sigma_1(\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3) + \omega_5 \sigma_1(\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_6) + \omega_3^2 + \omega_4^2 \sigma_1 + \omega_5^2 \sigma_2) + 2\beta_m v_2 \omega_9(\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 + \omega_4 + \omega_5 + \omega_5)]$$

$$Q_4 = 2\beta_{vm} v_8 \omega_7 [\omega_3 + \omega_4 \sigma_1 + \omega_5 \sigma_2] \text{ and } b = v_2 \omega_9 b_m > 0$$

Hence, it follows from the theorem by Castillo-Chavez and Song (2004) that the malaria-only model (2.26) undergoes backward bifurcation at $R_{0m} = 1$ whenever $Q_4 > Q_3$ (2.40)

The result is summarized below

Theorem 2.3:

The malaria-only model (2.26) undergoes a backward bifurcation at $R_{0m} = 1$ whenever the inequality (2.40) holds.

It is worth stating that for both the dengue-only model (2.12) and the malaria-only model (2.26), the DFE of both sub-models (ε_d and ε_m respectively) are not globally-asymptotically stable

when the associated reproduction numbers (R_{0d} and R_{0m} respectively) are less than unity, owing

to the phenomenon of backward bifurcation. Consequently, this study shows that the control of malaria (dengue) spread in a population when $R_{0m} < 1$ ($R_{0d} < 1$) will depend on the initial sizes

of the sub-populations of the malaria-only model (dengue-only model).

2.5 The Case of Prompt and Accurate Diagnosis of Malaria

In this case we assume that $k = 1$, that is individuals exposed are diagnosed and treated, so that

there are no misdiagnosed or undiagnosed infectives. Thus, the new model is given by the following system

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} = \Lambda_h + PR_m - (\lambda_m + \mu_n)S_h$$

$$\frac{dE_m}{dt} = \lambda_m S_h - (k + \mu_h)E_m$$

$$\frac{dI_m^D}{dt} = kE_m - (\tau_m + \mu_n + d_m)I_m^D$$

$$\frac{dR_m}{dt} = \tau_m I_m^D - (P + \mu_h)R_m \quad (2.41)$$

$$\frac{dM_s}{dt} = \Lambda_m - (\lambda_{hm} + \mu_m)M_s$$

$$\frac{dM_e}{dt} = \lambda_{hm}M_s - (\delta_2 + \mu_m)M_e$$

$$\frac{dM_i}{dt} = \delta_2 M_e - \mu_m M_i$$

where $\lambda_m = \frac{\beta_m b_m M_i}{N_h}$, $\lambda_{hm} = \frac{\beta_{vm} b_m I_m^D}{N_h}$ and $N_h = S_h + E_m + I_m^D + R_m$

$$N_m = M_s + M_e + M_i$$

Consider the region

$$\Omega_m^* = \begin{cases} (S_h, E_m, I_m^D, R_m) \in \mathbb{R}_+^4: N_h \leq \frac{\Lambda_n}{\mu_n} \\ (M_s, M_e, M_i) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3: N_m \leq \frac{\Lambda_m}{\mu_m} \end{cases} \quad (2.42)$$

It can be easily shown as done before that the region Ω_m^* is positively invariant and a global attractor of all positive solution of sub-model (2.41). Thus, it is sufficient to consider the dynamics of model (2.41) in Ω_m^* .

2.5.1 Stability of the DFE

The DFE of the malaria-only model (2.41) with prompt and accurate diagnosis is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_m^* &= (S_h^{**}, E_m^*, I_m^{D**}, R_m^{**}, M_s^{**}, M_i^{**}) \\ &= \left(\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}, 0, 0, 0, \frac{\Lambda_m}{\mu_m}, 0, 0 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.43)$$

Thus, the associated next generation matrices are given by

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \beta_m b_m \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_m b_m \Lambda_m \mu_n}{\Lambda_h \mu_m} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$V^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} k + \mu_h & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ k & \zeta_m + \mu_h + d_m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta_2 + \mu_m & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \delta_2 & \mu_m \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\rho_2 = k + \mu_n$, $\rho_3 = \tau_m + \mu_n + d_m$, $\rho_4 = \rho + \mu_n$, $\rho_5 = \delta_2 + \mu_m$

It follows that the reproduction number for accurate diagnosis, denoted by R_m^a is given by

$$R_m^a = \rho(FV^{-1})$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{\beta_{vm}\beta_m b_m^2 k \delta_2 \Lambda_m \mu_h}{\mu_m^2 \Lambda_h (k + \mu_h)(\tau_m + \mu_h + d_m)(\delta_2 + \mu_m)}} \quad (2.44)$$

Lemma 2.7

The DFE of the malaria-only model with prompt and accurate diagnosis (2.41), ε_m^* is LAS if

$R_m^a < 1$ and unstable if $R_m^a > 1$.

The threshold quantity, R_m^a represents the average number of cases that one case can produce if introduced into a population where all individuals who acquire malaria infection are diagnosed.

2.5.2 Endemic Equilibrium

In order to find the endemic equilibria of model (2.41), let $\varepsilon_1 = (S_h^{**}, E_m^{**}, I_m^{D**}, R_m^{**}, M_s^{**}, M_e^{**}, M_i^{**})$ represent any arbitrary endemic equilibrium of model

(2.4). Further, let

$$\lambda_m^{**} = \frac{\beta_m b_m M_i^{**}}{\mu_h^{**}} \quad (2.45)$$

and $\lambda_{hm}^{**} = \frac{\beta_{vm} b_m I_m^{D**}}{N_h^{**}} \quad (2.46)$

be the forces of infection of humans and vectors at steady state respectively. Solving the equations in (2.41) at steady states gives

$$S_h = \frac{\Lambda_h \rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4}{\rho_1 \rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 - \rho \tau_m k \lambda_m}, \quad E_m = \frac{\Lambda_h \rho_3 \rho_4 \lambda_m}{\rho_1 \rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 - \rho \tau_m k \lambda_m}, \quad I_m^D = \frac{\Lambda_h k \rho_4 \lambda_m}{\rho_1 \rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 - \rho \tau_m k \lambda_m}$$

$$R_m = \frac{\Lambda_n k \tau_m \lambda_m}{\rho_1 \rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 - \rho \tau_m k \lambda_m} \quad (2.47)$$

$$M_s = (\Lambda_m (\rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \tau_m \lambda_m)) / \{\beta_{vm} b_m k \rho_4 \lambda_m + \mu_m (\rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \tau_m \lambda_m)\}$$

$$M_e = (\beta_{vm} b_m k \rho_4 \Lambda_m \lambda_m) / \{\rho_5 [\beta_{vm} b_m k \rho_4 \lambda_m + \mu_m (\rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \tau_m \lambda_m)]\}$$

$$M_i = (\beta_{vm} b_m k \delta_2 \rho_4 \Lambda_m \lambda_m)$$

$$/ \{\mu_m \rho_5 [\beta_{vm} b_m k \rho_4 \lambda_m + \mu_m (\rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 + \rho_3 \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \rho_4 \lambda_m + k \tau_m \lambda_m)]\}$$

substituting (2.47) and (2.46) into (2.45), shows that the non-zero equilibria of the model satisfy the following quadratic: $\lambda_m^{**} [b_2 (\lambda_m^{**})^2 + b_1 (\lambda_m^{**}) + b_0] = 0$ (2.48)

$$\text{where } b_2 = \mu_m^2 \Lambda_n \rho_5 (2k \rho_4 (\rho_3 \rho_4 + \tau_m \rho_3 + \tau_m k) + k^2 (\rho_4^2 + \tau_m^2) + \rho_3^2 \rho_4^2)$$

$$b_1 = \mu_m \Lambda_n \beta_{vm} b_m k \rho_4 \rho_5 (\rho_3 \rho_4 + k \rho_4 + k \tau_m) + \beta_{vm} \beta_m b_m^2 k \delta_2 \rho_4 \Lambda_m (k \rho \tau_m + \rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4) + 2\mu_m^2 \Lambda_n \rho_2 \rho_3 \rho_4 \rho_5 (\rho_3 \rho_4 + k \rho_4 + k \tau_m)$$

$$b_0 = \mu_m^2 \Lambda_n \rho_2^2 \rho_3^2 \rho_4^2 \rho_5 (1 - (R_m^a)^2)$$

The positive endemic equilibria of model (2.41) are obtained by solving for λ_m^{**} from the quadratic equation (2.48) and substituting the results into the expression in (2.41). From the above quadratic (2.48), clearly, the coefficient b_2 of (2.48) is always positive and b_0 is positive (negative) if R_m^a is less than (greater than) unity, respectively. Thus, we establish the result given below.

Lemma 2.7

The malaria-only model (2.41) with prompt and accurate diagnosis has

- (i) a unique endemic equilibrium if $b_0 < 0 \Rightarrow R_m^a > 1$,
- (ii) a unique endemic equilibrium if $b_1 < 0$ and $b_0 = 0$ or $b_1^2 - 4b_0b_2 = 0$,
- (iii) two endemic equilibria if $b_0 > 0, b_1 < 0$ and $b_1^2 - 4b_0b_2 > 0$;
- (iv) no endemic equilibrium otherwise

From case (i), the model has a unique endemic equilibrium whenever $R_m^a > 1$. Case (iii) indicates the possibility of backward bifurcation. To check this, the discriminant $b_1^2 - 4b_0b_2$ is set to zero and solved for the critical value of R_m^a , denoted by R_c , given by

$$R_c = \sqrt{1 - \frac{b_1^2}{4b_2\rho_2^2\rho_3^2\rho_4^2\rho_5\mu_m^2\Lambda_h}} \quad (2.49)$$

Thus, backward bifurcation would occur for values of R_m such that $R_c < R_m^a < 1$.

Lemma 2.8:

The malaria only model (2.41) with prompt and accurate diagnosis undergoes backward bifurcation when case (iii) of lemma 2.7 holds and $R_c < R_m^a < 1$.

2.6 Analysis of the Malaria-Dengue Coinfection Model

Having analyzed the dynamics of the two sub-models, the full malaria-dengue model (2.1) is now considered. The DFE is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_0 &= (S_h, E_m, E_d, I_d, I_m^D, I_m^M, I_m^U, I_{md}, I_{md}^M, I_{md}^D, R_d, R_m, M_s, M_e, M_i, D_s, D_e, D_i) \\ &= \left(\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h}, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, \frac{\Lambda_d}{\mu_d}, 0, 0 \right) \quad (2.41) \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to show, using the next generation matrix method (as in section 2.3), that the associated reproduction number for the full malaria-dengue (2.1) denoted by R_{MD} is given by

$$R_{MD} = \max\{R_{0m}, R_{0d}\} \quad (2.42)$$

Hence, we have the following result.

Lemma 2.7

The DFE of the Malaria-Dengue model (2.1), given by (2.41), is locally asymptotically stable if $R_{MD} < 1$, and unstable if $R_{MD} > 1$.

3. Numerical Simulation

The malaria-dengue model (2.1) is numerically simulated to illustrate the effect of varying some key parameters related to diagnosis and misdiagnosis. The parameter values listed in table 3.1 are used for the simulations, otherwise specific parameter values used for the simulations are stated in the caption of each figure.

3.1 Demographic Parameters

The numerical simulation of model (2.1) will be based on demographic parameter relevant to Nigeria. The total population in Nigeria in 2019 is estimated at 200,963,599 [29]. It follows that at disease-free equilibrium, $\frac{\Lambda_h}{\mu_h} = 200,963,599$. The average lifespan of a Nigerian is assumed to be 50 years [3,31] so

that $\mu_n = 0.02$. the average recruitment rate is $\Lambda_n = 4,019,272$ per year. The following parameter

values were used in simulating the model:

Table 3.1 Parameter Values

Parameter	Nominal Value	Reference
Λ_h	4,019,272 year ⁻¹	[29]
Λ_m	10,000,000 year ⁻¹	[30]
Λ_d	10,000,000 year ⁻¹	[8]
N_n	0.02 year ⁻¹	[31]
μ_m	0.75 year ⁻¹	[19]
μ_d	0.365 year ⁻¹	[30]
β_{vm}	0.5 year ⁻¹	[19]
β_{vd}	0.09 year ⁻¹	[8]
β_m	0.75 year ⁻¹	[32]
β_d	0.833 year ⁻¹	[8]
b_m	0.13 year ⁻¹	[32]
b_d	0.12 year ⁻¹	Assumed
k	0.6	Assumed

ε	0.2	Assumed
σ	0.8	Assumed
τ_m	0.56 year ⁻¹	[19]
τ_d	0.44 year ⁻¹	Assumed
d_m	0.001 year ⁻¹	Assumed
d_1	0.0365 year ⁻¹	Assumed
$\phi_1, \phi_3, \phi_4, \phi_5$	0 – 1	
ϕ_2, ϕ_6, ϕ_7	0 – 1	
θ_2, θ_4	0 – 1	
θ_1, θ_3	0 – 1	
ζ_1, ζ_2	0 – 1	
ψ_1, ψ_2, ψ_3	1 – 2	
δ_1	0 – 1	
δ_2	0 – 1	

Figure 1 shows the effect of malaria diagnosis on co-infected individuals. Clearly, we observe that if individuals are not diagnosed at all, the number of co-infected individuals will increase to a point where it takes a longer period for the coinfection to die out. With prompt and accurate diagnosis, the number of co-infected cases continues to reduce at a steady pace and within a short period of time the coinfection will be eliminated.

Figure 1: simulation of model (2.1) with varying rate of diagnosis

Figure 2 reveals the effect of varying the rate of malaria misdiagnosis on the co-infected class. We observe that with maximum number of misdiagnosed cases of malaria infection, the number of co-infected cases will increase. If all malaria cases are diagnosed accurately and promptly, then the number of co-infected individuals will be drastically reduced.

Figure 2: simulation of model (2.1) varying the rate of misdiagnosis

Clearly, focusing on prompt and accurate diagnosis of malaria infection is beneficial in reducing the population of malaria-dengue co-infected individuals. This will also increase the number of malaria infected individuals that will be treated as well as those that will recover from the disease.

Figure 3: Backward bifurcation diagram for the malaria only model (3.54), showing the force of infection against the reproduction number (R_{0m}).

Fig. 4: Backward bifurcation diagram for the dengue only model (3.33), showing the force of infection against the reproduction number (R_{0d}).

Figure 5: plots of the number of malaria infected individuals, dengue infected and co-infected individuals.(a) Here the malaria treatment rate (τ_m) for infected individuals is varied from 0 to 1. (b) the dengue treatment rate (τ_d) for infected individuals is varied from 0-1 (c) The malaria treatment rate (τ_m) for recovered individuals is varied from 0 to 1

4. DISCUSSION

A deterministic model for investigating the effect of misdiagnosis of malaria on the transmission dynamics of malaria-dengue coinfection in a population has been formulated and analyzed.

Figure 1 shows the effect of malaria diagnosis on co-infected individuals. Clearly, we observe that if individuals are not diagnosed at all, the number of co-infected individuals will increase to a point where it takes a longer period for the coinfection to die out. With prompt and accurate diagnosis, the number of co-infected cases continues to reduce at a steady pace and within a short period of time the coinfection will be eliminated. Figure 2 reveals the effect of varying the rate of malaria misdiagnosis on the co-infected class. We observe that with maximum number of misdiagnosed cases of malaria infection, the number of co-infected cases will increase. If all malaria cases are diagnosed accurately and promptly, then the number of co-infected individuals will be drastically reduced. Clearly, focusing on prompt and accurate diagnosis of malaria infection is beneficial in reducing the population of malaria-dengue co-infected individuals. This will also increase the number of malaria infected individuals that will be treated as well as those that will recover from the disease.

We summarize the major theoretical and epidemiological findings as follows:

- The dengue only model (2.12) exhibits the phenomenon of backward bifurcation at $R_d = 1$ whenever a certain condition hold.
- The malaria only model (2.20) undergoes the phenomenon of backward bifurcation at $R_{om} = 1$ whenever a certain condition hold.
- The malaria only model (2.4) with prompt and accurate diagnosis of malaria undergoes backward bifurcation when $R_c < R_m < 1$.
- The DFE of the malaria-dengue coinfection model (2.1) is locally asymptotically stable if $R_{MD} < 1$.
- Numerical simulation suggests that with prompt and accurate diagnosis of malaria, the coinfection will be drastically reduced if not eliminated with time. This will also increase the number of malaria infectives that will be treated as well as those that will recover from malaria infection.

This study has shown the need for prompt and accurate diagnosis of malaria and its effect on the transmission dynamics of malaria-dengue coinfection. Malaria-dengue coinfection is more severe than single infection and since they show the same clinical symptoms, it is difficult to differentiate one from the other. Hence there is need to correctly diagnose malaria infection as it is more common than the dengue infection.

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Declarations of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest whatsoever.

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